

DIVIDING OF THE SEMANTICS OF SOMATIC UNITS OF A PART OF THE HUMAN BODY INTO LEXICAL GROUPS (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES)

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Abstract: The article identifies and describes lexical units denoting parts of the body in the phraseological funds of the Uzbek and English languages. The totality of these lexical units is presented in the structure of the lexico-semantic field, the construction of which is based on the semantics of the lexical unit, the possibility of its figurative use and taking into account fixed associations.

Key words: somatism, phraseological unit, lexical-semantic group, lexical-semantic field.

Phraseological units with somatisms in Uzbek and English are characterized by high frequency and have a variety of structural models. The frequency of these units is explained by the property of human nature to realize itself as a fragment of a holistic picture of the world, as well as by the primary naive ideas of a person about himself and the world around him. According to O. A. Borgoyakova, awareness of oneself, one's place in the world and society, the definition of "oneself as a person, a person began with sensations arising directly through the sense organs and parts of his own body" [1, c.169]. Yu. S. Stepanov notes that the importance of a person in the Universe determines his "parametrization" and a broad description by linguistic means: thousands of words serve as the name of a person, his social role, body parts, appearance, character, psycho-emotional and intellectual components. Phraseological funds of the Uzbek and English languages fix various nominations of a person, his body parts, character traits, appearance. By a phraseological unit with a somatic component, we mean a phraseological fund unit, the component composition of which includes a lexical component denoting parts of the human body. Also, in the framework of this work, we refer to somatisms the designation of internal organs and vital systems of a person. Taking into account the semantic, associative, and figurative components of the lexical unit will expand the range of somatisms.

The set of lexical units that can act as a designation of a part of the body or human organ can be systematized and presented in the structure of the lexico-semantic field (LSP) with the corresponding zones. The construction of the LSP in this work is carried out based on the semantics of the lexical unit, the possibility of figurative use of the lexical unit and the associations assigned to it

are taken into account. Lexical units are distributed according to the corresponding lexico-semantic groups (LSG) and distributed in the structure of the LSP of somatisms. The nuclear zone of the LSP of somatisms of English and Uzbek phraseological funds includes the names of parts of the human body, the perinuclear zone includes the names of internal organs, various hairline, elements of vital systems, and the names of animal body parts are located in the periphery zone. The human body, as well as the body of animals, in the first place, those that were domesticated, or those that a person encountered while hunting, turned out to be one of the most accessible objects for observation, comparison and description. This fact explains a significant number of examples of phraseological units with somatic components located in the nuclear and perinuclear, as well as peripheral zones of the LSP of somatisms. In the zone of the extreme periphery of the LSP of somatisms, in our opinion, there may be units denoting the names of clothes that are usually associated with one or another part of the body. These units are not somatisms, but can be correlated with them (somatisms) through the accounting of associations. In this case, we are approaching the point of view of E. M. Vereshchagin, V. G. Kostomarov, according to which somatism is "any meaningful sign, position or movement of the face or the whole body of a person" [2, c.24]. Taking into account the semantics of language units that can act as a designation of a body part or organ, associations assigned to them, as well as the possibility of figurative use of a lexical unit, allow us to divide English and Russian lexical units into several lexico-semantic groups (LSG), which have their own zones in the structure of the LSP of somatisms in each of the phraseological funds. The first LSG consists of lexical units denoting the trunk, upper and lower limbs, head, as well as elements located in the indicated parts of the human body (heel, neck, eye, arm, leg, hand, elbow, head, ears, mouth, foot (feet), nose, shoulder, back, fingers, thumb, face, cheek, chin, toe, lips, palm, body, fist, breast, wrist) and (legs, neck, back, head, eye(s), ears, cheek , palm, arm, elbow, side, mouth, face, nose, abdomen, forehead, shoulders, finger, little finger, chest, lips, body, heels, back of the head, knee, crown, nostril). These units in the construction of the LSP of somatisms of the phraseological fund of the English and Russian languages are located in its nuclear zone. Somatisms related to the lower limbs in the phraseological foundations of both languages are (foot (feet), heel, leg, toe, legs, heels, heels, knee): show a clean pair of heels — only the heels sparkled, be light on one's feet - to have a light gait; walk on the heels ; to drag one's feet ; only the heels sparkled. The meaning of Uzbek and English phraseological units

with somatisms denoting lower limbs often conveys information about various ways of walking and moving. At the same time, English and Uzbek phraseological units with somatisms denoting lower limbs can also implement semantics not related to movement: dig in one's heels - give a decisive rebuff ; stick in one's heels - stubborn; on a friendly footing - on friendly terms. The torso is represented by the following somatisms (neck, shoulders, back, body, breast, neck, back, side, belly, shoulders, chest, body): put smth on smb's shoulders - to put on someone , shoulder, break your neck ; stand up with your chest. The head, as you know, is responsible for the perception of information, thought processes and behavior. In the phraseological fund of the Uzbek and English languages, there are a significant number of examples of phraseological units with the component head / head: and clear head is a bright head; have a good head on one's shoulders - have a head on your shoulders [3, p. 221]; blame with a sick head on a healthy one. Eyes, ears, nose, etc. are located within the head. Represented in phraseological funds are (chin, cheeks, face, lips, nose, ears, mouth, eyes, eyes, ears, cheek, mouth, face, nose, crown, lips, back of the head, forehead, nostril): keep a straight face - keep a serious look [3, c. 282]; pull a long face - look sad [3, p. 404]; paint rushed into the face [6, c.211].

A feature of the use of somatisms in the phraseological fund of the Uzbek language is their more fractional nomination within the head (back of the head, forehead, crown of the nostril): scratch the back of the head, ears on top, as well as the presence of synonymous designations of body parts that differ stylistically (head, mug, zenki, mouth, eye, snout, forehead). Lexical units denoting internal organs, including organs of mental activity, various hairline, as well as elements of human vital systems, we refer to the second LSH and are located in the perinuclear zone of the LSH of somatisms (blood, heart, bones, mind, nails, eyebrow, eyelash, tooth (teeth), lung, throat, hair, brow, tongue, brain, skin, muscles, soul, tongue, throat, heart, eyebrow, shoulder blade, mind, blood, soul (spirit), hair, brains, skin, intestines, veins, hamstrings, bones, mustaches). The lexical units of this group designate the elements of the body or living substance that are extremely important for a person, without which the functioning of a living organism is impossible: at the top of one's lungs — loudly , blood runs cold in the veins ; hair stand on end. This group also includes lexical units denoting mental abilities, intelligence (mind, brain, mind, brains): bring to mind - remember live with your own mind set the brains . At the same time, the soul in both languages is considered precisely as an internal organ: “the soul in a naive-linguistic representation is perceived as a kind of invisible organ, localized

somewhere in the chest and “managing” the inner life of a person”. Many of the lexical units, the main meaning of which is the name of an organ or part of the body, are used in phraseological units about morality, sincerity, eternal human values (heart, mind, bone, soul, head): from the heart - from a pure heart peaceofmind - peace of mind to the marrow of one's bones - to the depths of the soul. The lexeme soul in many cases turns out to be synonymous with lexemes (heart, mind, spirit, head): cut smb to the soul - to hurt to the depths of the soul; prey on one's mind - torment someone's soul, akindred spirit — kindred spirit, heart and soul - with all my soul [3, p. 237], and the lexeme blood denotes blood ties, human nature: be in one's blood — to be an heir [3, p. 47]; in cold blood - cold-blooded.

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